

Literature Review: Training Service Quality of Universities in Vietnam

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Abstract:

The objective of the article is to evaluate previous studies on the quality of training services of universities. The author has conducted a review of studies related to measuring training service quality, an overview of studies related to the influence of training service quality on student satisfaction. From the overview of the studies, the author discusses and proposes future research directions

Keywords: Training service quality, student satisfaction

1. Introduction

In the world, the quality of products and services has long been considered a key factor to ensure the success and effective competitive advantage of enterprises. An organization that pays special attention to the quality of products and services will be able to make a difference compared to other organizations and it is inevitable that this organization will have long-term competitive advantages (Moore, 1987). Now, higher education institutions (HEs) are recognized as part of the service industry (Galeeva, 2016) and are becoming a fast-growing, competitive industry to cater to the growing demand of society (Latif et al., 2017). Dynamic national, regional and global developments have forced HEs to rapidly transform and these changes have received increasing attention over the past two decades (de Jager and Gbadamosi, 2013). As students will pay for their educational expenses, HEs must move from being product-based to selling to being customer-oriented (Angell et al., 2008) and in a competitive market, improving service quality is essential for the survival of HEs (Vieira et al., 2008).

Students are considered primary customers of higher education (Crawford, 1991) while employers, government and families are considered secondary customers (Madu et al., 1994), Sirvanci, 1996). Student service experience is complex and different from that of consumers in any service industry (Latif et al., 2017), so there must be a unique method to assess the level of service quality. services in this industry (Ushantha & Kumara, 2016). Studies have attempted to develop a service quality measurement scale in HE (LeBlanc & Nguyen, 1997; Ford et al., 1999; Hill et al., 2003; Lagrosen et al., 2004; Firdaus, 2006; Senthilkumar and Arulraj, 2011; Asif et al., 2013; Teeroovengadum et al., 2016) but so far there is no consensus on the main factors constituting the quality of training services, especially for HEs in developing countries (Asif et al., 2013).

The internationalization of higher education (Harvey and Williams, 2010; Sultan and Wong, 2010) was accompanied by an increase in the number of private universities (Halai, 2013) and a decrease in the state budget for public universities. (Quinn et al., 2009) makes the higher education market increasingly competitive. Therefore, just as business organizations have an obligation to continuously delight their customers in order to thrive (Calvo-Porrall et al., 2013), universities need to satisfy their students. them (Lagrosen et al., 2004; Srikanthan and Dalrymple, 2007) by providing high-quality educational services. One strategy that is attracting public attention to improve the quality of higher education services is the student-centered approach (Stodnick & Rogers, 2008). The core idea of this strategy is to treat students as customers and the university must do its best to provide the best educational service to students (Stodnick & Rogers, 2008), which will make students satisfied and loyal to their university (Martinez-Arguelles & Batalla-Busquets, 2016). The student satisfaction

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approach can be a tool to create a bridge between academic and market-oriented perspectives on how to improve the quality of higher education (Wiers-Jenssen et al., 2002).

In Vietnam, higher education is associated with the history of Eastern higher education, in which the goal of education is to train elites with a very strict hierarchy and examination system. In such a system, the teacher plays a central role, so there is information asymmetry, meaning that the school and the lecturer always have more information than the students and have great decision-making power (on learning outcomes) for students. Currently, stemming from the need to go to school and the need for trained workers of socio-economic development, Vietnamese higher education has had a shift from "elite" higher education to higher education. "mass" higher education, from universities for the few to the many, for the many. However, much of the mindset of elitist education still exists. In addition, with the emergence of many universities, in order to compete and retain students, many lecturers tend to satisfy short-term student satisfaction (for high scores, positive rewards, etc.) but not sure to bring about the overall satisfaction of the quality of training services of students. Clearly, there is a contradiction between the immediate satisfaction of students and the delivery of quality training services in the long term.

2. Literature review

2.1. Studies on factors measuring training service quality

There are many studies on the factors measuring the quality of training services. Joseph and Joseph (1997) conducted a survey of business students in New Zealand on perceptions of the quality of educational services. Research results have identified seven factors determining service quality: (1) Tangible means; (2) Cost/time; (3) Reputation of the university; (4) Training program; (5) Career opportunities; (6) Location; (7) Other: word of mouth, family and colleagues/friends. On that basis, the study provided implications for educational administrators and made some suggestions for future research.

LeBlanc and Nguyen (1997) measure service quality in education with data collected from 388 students. The study has identified seven factors that students evaluate service quality in descending order of importance: (1) Reputation; (2) Administrative staff; (3) Lecturers; (4) Curriculum; (5) Responsiveness; (6) Tangibles and (7) Access to facilities. The study also provides implications for quality control and for achieving high efficiency in the education business.

Research by Hill et al. (2003) aims to determine students' perceptions of quality experiences in higher education. Research results have shown four factors constituting the quality of higher education: (1) Quality of lecturers; (2) Students participate in learning; (3) Social/emotional support system; and (4) Library and information technology resources; where the quality of the faculty and the student support system are the most influential factors in providing quality education.

Firdaus (2005), in the study of higher education service quality, developed a model to measure training service quality. This model is built by comparison method with SERVPERF model – a model developed by Cronin and Taylor (1992) from SERVQUAL (Parasuraman et al., 1985) to assess the strengths and limitations of each model. paradigm. Through a survey of six public and private schools in Malaysia, Firdaus (2005) shows that there are five groups of factors determining the quality of training services including: (1) Teaching (Academic aspects), (2) Behavior Non-academic aspects, (3) Reputation, (4) Access, and (5) Program issues.

Chen et al (2007) studied the quality of higher education in Cambodia and explored the potential factors leading to the quality of higher education, and identified five main factors that are considered to be relevant in the provision of higher education. quality in higher education: (1) Training programs and extracurricular activities; (2) Teaching faculty; (3) Budget; (4) Facilities; and (5) Interactive system.

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Gamage et al (2008) determine students' perceptions of the quality of services provided by private universities in Thailand and Japan and how these factors affect university choice. The results show that three factors affect students' decision to choose a university, including (1) Academic aspect: reflected in the quality of the teaching staff, the quality of the training program, the university's reputation; (2) Non-academic aspects: related to financial aid and tuition, counseling and support services, employment services, complaints procedures; and (3) Facility aspect: related to university facilities, library and computer equipment, student organizations and recreational facilities.

Also in a study assessing the quality of higher education services, Sultan and Wong (2010) developed another scale called Performance-Based Higher Education (PHed) consisting of 67 items with eight dimensions edge: (1) Reliability; (2) Efficiency; (3) Ability; (4) Performance; (5) Capacity; (6) Guarantee; (7) Unusual situation management and (8) Textbook.

Jain et al. (2011) research on the modeling of service quality in higher education has built a service quality model based on the concept of service quality. Research shows that service quality consists of two main groups of factors: program quality, including: (1) teaching quality, input quality, interoperability, learning facilities; (2) aspects of administrative and logistical management including: input quality (quality of learners, teaching staff, administrative staff, facilities), training process (teaching, learning) and administrative work), output quality (exam results, jobs and income levels).

In the study with a narrower research object of Charles et al. (2013) on the quality of training services for MBA programs, the majority of studies assessing the quality of the MBA program in particular and the quality of training. In general, all use SERVQUAL, SERVPERF and HEDPERF models and confirm the factors that make up the quality of an MBA program, including curriculum content, teaching quality, program reliability, learning facilities. training and outcomes, but two MBA service quality criteria, program management and organizational image, have not been modeled for measurement.

Latif et al (2017) based on exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) found six components of service quality in HE, named HiEduQual model including HiEduQual. including: (1) Quality of teachers; (2) Administrative services; (3) Knowledge services; (4) Activities; (5) Continuous improvement and (6) Quality leadership.

2.2. Studies on the influence of training service quality on student satisfaction

Service quality and customer satisfaction are fundamentally different concepts. While service quality is a general attitude, satisfaction is linked by many transaction-specific (Patterson and Johnson, 1993; Rowley, 1997; Aldridge and Rowley, 1998; Robinson, 1999). Parasuraman et al. (1993) said that service quality and satisfaction have differences, the most basic difference is the issue of "cause and effect". Research conducted by Parasuraman et al. (1985, 1988) provides a basic foundation for measuring the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction. They argue that perceived service quality leads to customer satisfaction, and therefore, these authors use the gap between customer expectations of a provider's performance and actual perceived experience. about that performance. This means, if the customer perceives the service to be of high quality, then the customer will be satisfied. Cronin and Taylor (1992) also agree with this view and through the SERVPERF scale concluded that perceived service quality can predict customer satisfaction and customer satisfaction plays a strong role. stronger in future purchase intention than service quality. Many subsequent studies show that service quality is the cause of customer satisfaction and is closely related to customer satisfaction (Spreng and Mackoy, 1996; Oliver, 1993; Kim et al., 2004; Seth et al., 2008; Hanzae & Nasimi, 2012). In addition, some other authors (Bitner, 1990; Bolton and Drew, 1991a, b) see this relationship in the opposite direction and suggest that, if customers are satisfied with the service provided to them, they will find it to be of the highest value. However, this view does not receive much support from the authors. In general, perceived service quality is a prerequisite for satisfaction (Spreng and Mckoy, 1996).

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In the context of higher education, many scholars have studied the impact of different aspects of training service quality on student satisfaction. Browne et al. (1998) and Guolla (1999) indicate that the quality of training services is an antecedent of student satisfaction. Positive perception of training service quality can lead to student satisfaction and then satisfied students can attract new students through positive word of mouth to inform acquaintances and friends, and they may return to university to take other courses (Marzo-Navarro et al., 2005; Wiers-Jenssen et al., 2002; Mavondo et al., 2004; Schertzer and Schertzer, 2004).

Winsted (2000); Zeithaml et al. (1990) confirm that service providers will only be able to enter service competitions to satisfy customers if they know what their customers want. If universities knew how their students perceive the services offered, they might be able to accommodate their services to a specific extent. This has a positive impact on service quality on students' perceptions and their satisfaction levels. In other words, the supplier is the one who guides the consumer's consumption trends. As society develops, suppliers often offer products and services of higher quality than customers' common sense and understanding. The same is true with university training services.

Oldfield and Baron (2000) also suggest that there is a tendency to view higher education service quality from the perception of an organization. They suggest that universities pay more attention to what students want, rather than collecting data based on what the university finds its students find important. Similarly, Joseph et al. (2005) show that research on service quality in universities has relied entirely on input from school members while excluding input from students themselves. They believe that traditional methods of deciding what constitutes service quality (e.g. deciding what is most important to students) rests entirely in the hands of administrative staff and faculty. Joseph et al., (2005). Therefore, the authors suggest that training managers should focus on understanding the needs of students, who are the primary and specific target customers. Similarly, Douglas et al. (2006) suggest that student experience and their improvement should be at the forefront of any monitoring of the quality of higher education.

Ham and Hayduk (2003) confirmed that there is a positive correlation between perception of training service quality and student satisfaction. Student satisfaction plays an important role in the success of a university and can serve as an essential tool in enhancing its perceived service quality (Firdaus, 2006a). Browne et al. (1998) and Guolla (1999) show that students' perception of training service quality is a prerequisite for student satisfaction. Positive perception of training service quality can lead to student satisfaction and satisfied students can then attract new students by engaging in active word-of-mouth communication to inform others, acquaintances and friends, and they may return to university to take other courses (Marzo-Navarro et al., 2005; Wiers- Jenssen et al., 2002; Mavondo et al., 2004; Schertzer and Schertzer), 2004).

In a study conducted by Firdaus (2005), it was found that in the context of higher education, the main determinants of student satisfaction include academic and non-academic aspects, program-related, accessibility, and reputational issues. Another study conducted by Afzal et al. (2010) explains that there are eight dimensions of higher education service quality including design, delivery and assessment, learning facility, non-structural facilities, academics, accreditation, instruction, student representation, learning opportunities, and group size. The teaching skills of lecturers and their interactions with students can also lead to student satisfaction (Bitner and Zeithaml, 1996). This is supported by Kuh and Hu (2001), who suggested that student satisfaction is significantly influenced by effective interactions between students and faculty. Similarly, Kara and De Shields (2004) state that determinants of student satisfaction include service quality aspects such as faculty performance, counselor performance, and classes. In addition, Brochado (2009) compared HEdPERF with other alternative higher education service quality models and confirmed that the five dimensions of HEdPERF have a higher correlation with student satisfaction and intention. future behavior. Research by Ali et al (2017) continues to confirm that five aspects of HEdPERF have an influence on student satisfaction.

Hishamuddin et al (2008) also studied the relationship between service quality and student satisfaction. The study investigated 200 university students from two private schools in Malaysia with prepared questionnaires.

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However, this study only deals with students from private schools. In the study of learner satisfaction in higher education, Babar and Kashif (2010) focused on factors such as the professional knowledge of the lecturers, courses, learning environment and facilities. in the classroom. 350 students responded through a questionnaire with questions corresponding to a 5-point Likert scale. The results of the regression analysis show that all the influencing factors have an important and positive impact on student satisfaction with different levels, in which, the professional knowledge factor of lecturers has an important influence on student satisfaction.

Price et al. (2003) made a report on the impact of factors on the choice of university students. They surveyed several colleges for two years to determine student reasons for choosing a particular college. The two-year averages are pretty much the same - the top eight reasons are: the right course; computers available; library quality; teaching reputation; the availability of quiet areas; self-study area; quality of public transport in town/city and student-friendly attitude. Obviously, students' perception of university conditions is one of the main influences on their admission decision.

Coles (2002) found that student satisfaction was reduced when class sizes were larger in previous cohorts and when students were using required modules instead of optional modules.

Regarding the satisfaction of business administration students, DeShields et al (2005) showed eight outstanding factors constituting student satisfaction including: Self-confidence; Satisfaction with the instructions; Curriculum and classes; Satisfaction with the quality of teaching; Satisfaction with extracurricular activities and career opportunities; Satisfaction with consulting; teaching quality and feedback instruction; Satisfaction with computer room equipment; Student satisfaction with quality.

Douglas et al (2006) designed and used a questionnaire to measure student satisfaction at the Liverpool John Moores University School of Business and Law. The results show that there are 10 factors ranked in descending order of importance that affect student satisfaction, including: teaching ability of lecturers, professional qualifications of lecturers, information technology infrastructure, lectures, teaching assistants, teaching manuals, uniformity of teaching quality, learning resource centers, study guides and virtual learning environments.

Marcel et al (2014) suggest that student satisfaction is influenced by the extent to which higher education institutions meet or exceed their expectations. Research has shown a number of factors to assess student satisfaction, including: educational process (curriculum, training of teaching staff, examination policy), administrative staff, enrollment process (information, staff), faculty management, faculty image, library, general information, cafeteria, educational environment, tutors, cooperation between lecturers and business environment, international cooperation economic, recreational activities are supported by the faculty.

Martirosyan (2014) used a pragmatic, non-experimental approach to investigate the factors affecting student satisfaction in the university setting in AHEIs. Data were collected through self-reported questionnaires from students in nine public and three private institutions in different rural and urban areas of Armenia. The sample includes 372 respondents from 12 organizations whose geography covers the whole country for a relatively complete picture. Investigated factors related to student satisfaction include: demographics, faculty, learning experience, student support facilities, campus life and social integration.

3. Discussion and conclusion

Thus, it can be seen that service quality and satisfaction are topics that receive a lot of attention from researchers. Studies have shown that service quality and customer satisfaction are fundamentally different. They believe that customer satisfaction is influenced not only by perceived service quality but also by factors such as product quality, price, personal factors and contextual factors (Zeithaml et al., 2008).

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To measure the quality of training services, the quality of e-learning training services, studies have used very diverse sets of criteria. Some studies use the SERVQUAL scale of Parasuraman et al. (1985) or SERVPERF of Cronin and Taylor (1992); some studies use Firdaus's HEDPERF scale (2005) developed specifically for the field of higher education; In addition, many researches develop their own sets of scales on the basis of combining many different types of scales. The scales are all developed based on specific research contexts, so it is difficult to give a standard set of scales to measure the quality of higher education services in all countries. In Vietnam, there have been quite a few studies on the topic of quality and satisfaction in the field of higher education and the studies also apply existing scales in the world. However, the higher education context of each country can be a good suggestion to continue to search, research and develop new factors/scales. In Vietnam, academic results (shown on transcripts) are one of the important factors in assessing student satisfaction. When students achieve high results, that is, students are satisfied with the assessment of learning results, they will have positive evaluations about the training service aspect of the universities. Another important point in educational services is information asymmetry – that is, schools and teachers (suppliers) may know more than students. One of the potential areas of risk from asymmetric information is student grades, in which faculty members may give high marks (arbitrarily) in exchange for immediate satisfaction with academic performance, but are not It is unlikely that this has resulted in overall and long-term quality of education. In addition, fairness including clear regulations in the training process and the timely and complete provision of information to students are also factors to consider. Numerous studies have also shown that when individuals feel more confident in fairness, they are more satisfied with the outcomes they receive, even if the results have some adverse effect on them (Lind & Tyler, 1988). Thus, the above factors are almost not found in previous studies, the reason may be because these factors only occur in the context of higher education in Vietnam. Therefore, this is considered a research gap for the author to continue to exploit.

Vietnamese higher education is gradually opening up more and more with the emergence of more and more private universities. Although there are comparisons on the training quality of public and private universities, there are almost no official studies comparing the quality of training services at these two types of institutions. Especially schools in centrally-run cities and schools in small provinces have not had any research comparing these schools. Therefore, this study will compare, evaluate and analyze service quality and student satisfaction in two types of education and in two central-affiliated cities and provinces in Vietnam.

As the overview has analyzed, there are many approaches, concepts of "training service quality, e-learning training service quality" and "student satisfaction". The approach of Parasuraman et al. (1988) or Cronin and Taylor (1992) is an approach that is recognized and applied by many studies to measure service quality in most industries, but According to Firdaus (2005), when applying, from the basic measurement framework, we often have to ask to modify the scale to fit the specific situation and often have additional factors. Firdaus (2005) proposed the HEDPERF model to measure quality in higher education and a number of subsequent studies have shown that the HEDPERF model is an effective tool to measure the quality of higher education services. (Brochado, 2009; Sultan and Wong, 2010). However, to get a more general view of using the HEDPERF scale to measure perceived service quality from the perspective of university students worldwide, Silva et al (2017) reviewed All studies use this scale and find that HEDPERF is not really widely available, as only eleven articles were published between 2005 and 2016. Therefore, study service quality in this context. The university training scene needs further attention.

In the context of Vietnam's higher education environment, along with an overview of models for measuring training service quality and student satisfaction, in this study the author uses a combination of 3 models to measuring the quality of training services in Vietnam: (1) HedPERF model of Firdaus (2005); model of Gamage et al (2008) and (3) model of Jain et al (2013). These research models are carried out in the field of higher education and in developing countries in Asia with similar socio-economic contexts to Vietnam such as Malaysia (Firdaus, 2005), Thailand. Lan (Gamage et al., 2008), India (Jain et al., 2013). In these studies, the common variables to measure training service quality that affect student satisfaction are lecturer quality,

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training program quality, facilities, quality administrative staff, extracurricular activities and quality of support services (Joseph and Joseph, 1997; LeBanc and Nguyen, 1997; Abdullah, 2006; Gamage et al., 2008; Jain et al., 2013).

First of all, the quality of lecturers is a factor mentioned in many studies on training service quality and in the study of Firdaus (2005); Gamage et al (2008), this factor belongs to the academic aspect. In his research, the author proposes that the quality of lecturers is the first factor affecting student satisfaction. Next, the quality of training programs is mentioned in all three studies, in which Gamage et al (2008) include this factor in the academic aspect and Firdaus (2005) and Jain et al (2013) split into an independent element. Facilities are also a factor mentioned in many studies, in which Gamage et al (2008) suggest this factor is the combination of facilities, libraries, computer equipment; Firdaus (2005) is included in the reputation component and Jain et al (2013) splits into learning facilities and learning support facilities. In this study, the author proposes the physical factors including facilities for learning such as classrooms, libraries, computer rooms, etc. For non-academic aspects, many factors are mentioned such as: administrative staff (Firdaus, 2005), financial and tuition assistance, counseling and employment support services (Gamage et al., 2008) or non-academic processes (Jain et al., 2008). This is also an aspect that the author focuses on in this study. In addition, university reputation is of particular interest in the study of Firdaus (2005) and Gamage et al (2008), which shows the society's evaluation of universities and also contributes to the set of criteria evaluate the quality of training services of students.

Besides, although not common, training costs are also mentioned in some studies such as Joseph and Joseph (1997), Chen et al (2007). From a business point of view, if we consider education and training as a market, the correlation between price and quality of products and services receives a lot of attention from consumers. The view of high price – high quality has existed for a long time, however, in the context of higher education, this correlation is not necessarily so positive. At private universities, training costs are much higher than in public universities, but that cost is mainly to invest in facilities and learning environment, not to improve quality. Therefore, the quality of general training services of private universities is still not considered by the society to be equal to that of public universities. From a student perspective, students expect to receive good quality training services with a suitable tuition fee. Therefore, in this study, the author proposes a hypothesis about the relationship between the suitability of costs and student satisfaction.

Another aspect that also receives the attention of students when evaluating the quality of training services is fairness. This factor has also been proposed by many researchers such as Kwan and Ng (1999), Peng and Samah (2006) but is often named course assessment. Usami and Jamal (2013) found a special factor affecting employee job satisfaction called organizational justice, which is related to the fair treatment of employees. Colquitt et al. (2001) synthesized 183 studies related to the topic of equity and classified them into 3 main components: Distributive justice, procedural justice and comparative justice. Interactional justice, in which procedural justice is a concept referring to the perception of fairness towards policies and standards (Voorhees and Brady, 2005). Studies have also shown that when individuals feel more confident in fairness, they are more satisfied with the outcomes they receive, even if the results have some adverse effect on them (Lind and Tyler, 1988). For students, their satisfaction is based on the feeling of fair treatment of teachers and related departments in the process of information transmission, the listening of lecturers/staff to the students. student requirements and overall assessment consistency. Therefore, this study will examine the impact of equity on student satisfaction.

Student satisfaction is a composite measure based on satisfaction with the quality of the lecturers, the quality of the training programs, the facilities, the reputation of the university, etc. However, for students, a One of the most concerned aspects is whether learning outcomes are assessed fairly and accurately. In fact, it can be seen that this is one of the important aspects to measure student satisfaction. If satisfaction is considered as students' perception or perception of the values provided by the school's educational services, how perceived learning

outcomes are assessed is a direct factor that creates so student satisfaction. In a certain aspect, students think that the score shows the recognition as well as the fair assessment of the school for the learning and training process and thereby will increase the overall satisfaction with the quality of the service. training service of the school. The results of qualitative research also show that students attach great importance to the fair assessment of lecturers through grades. Therefore, in this study, the author separates the satisfaction variable on the assessment of learning outcomes from the student satisfaction variable and hypothesizes that this variable is an intermediate variable between the quality of lecturers, the quality of teachers and the quality of students. curriculum and equity with student satisfaction.

References

- i. Ali, F.; Zhou, Y.; Hussain, K.; Nair, P.K.; Ragavan, N.A. (2016), "Does higher education service quality effect student satisfaction, image and loyalty? A study of international students in Malaysian public universities", *Quality Assurance in Education*, Vol. 24, Iss 1, pp. 70-94.
- ii. Anderson, P.F. and Gerbing, D.W. (1998). "Structural equation modelling in practice: a review and recommended two-step approach". *Psychological Bulletin*, 103(3), pp.411-23.
- iii. Angell, R.J., Heffernan, T.W. and Megicks, P. (2008), "Service quality in postgraduate education", *Quality Assurance in Education*, Vol. 16 No. 3, pp. 236-254.
- iv. Appleton-Knapp, S.L. and Krentler, K.A. (2006), "Measuring student expectations and their effects on satisfaction: the importance of managing student expectations", *Journal of Marketing Education*, Vol. 28 No. 1, pp. 254-264.
- v. Arif, S. and Ilyas, M. (2013), "Quality of work-life model for teachers of private universities in Pakistan", *Quality Assurance in Education*, Vol. 21 No. 3, pp. 282-298.
- vi. Athiyaman, A. (1997), "Linking student satisfaction and service quality perceptions: the case of university education", *European Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 31 No. 7, pp. 528-40.
- vii. Becket, N. and Brookes, M. (2006), "Evaluating quality management in university departments", *Quality Assurance in Education*, Vol. 14 No. 2, pp. 123- 142.
- viii. Bitner, M.J. and Zeithaml, V.A. (1996), *Services Marketing*, McGraw-Hill, New York, NY.
- ix. Ministry of Education and Training, (2007). Decision No. 65/2007/QĐ-BGDĐT - Decision Promulgating Regulations on criteria for assessing the quality of higher education. Hanoi.
- x. Ministry of Education and Training, (2009). Report No. 760/BC-BGDĐT - Report on the development of the higher education system, solutions to ensure and improve training quality. Hanoi.
- xi. Brochado, A. (2009). "Comparing Alternative Instruments for Measuring Service Quality in Higher Education". *Quality Assurance in Education*, 17, 174-190.
- xii. Brokaw, A.J., Kennedy, W.A. and Merz, T.E. (2004), "Explaining student satisfaction", *Journal of Business Education*, Vol. 5 No. 1, pp. 10-20.
- xiii. Çerri, S (2012), "Assessing the quality of higher education services using a modified servqual scale", *Annales Universitatis Apulensis Series Oeconomica*, 14(2).
- xiv. Chen, C.Y., Sok, P. and Sok, K. (2007). "Benchmarking potential factors leading to education quality: A study of Cambodian higher education". *Quality Assurance in Education*, 15(2), pp.128-48.
- xv. Cheng, Y.C., & Tam, W.M. (1997). "Multi-models of quality in education". *Quality Assurance in Education*, 5 (1), 22-34.
- xvi. Chou, S. (2004), "Evaluating the service quality of undergraduate nursing education in Taiwan – using quality function deployment", *Nurse Education Today*, Vol. 24 No. 4, pp. 310-18.
- xvii. Churchill, J.G.A. (1979). "A paradigm for developing better measures of marketing constructs". *Journal of Marketing Research*, 26(1), pp.64-73.
- xviii. Clewes, D. (2003), "A student-centered conceptual model of service quality in higher education", *Quality in Higher Education*, Vol. 9 No. 1, pp. 69-85.

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- xix. Cronin J. J., Taylor S. A., (1992). "Measuring service quality: A reexamination and extension", *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 56, No. 3, pp. 55-68.
- xx. Dana, S.W., Brown, F.W. and Dodd, N.G. (2001), "Student perception of teaching effectiveness: a preliminary study of the effects of professors' transformational and contingent reward leadership behaviors", *Journal of Business Education*, Vol. 2 No. 1, pp. 53-70.
- xxi. Day, R. (1984), "Modelling choices among alternative responses to dissatisfaction", in Kinnear, T.C. (Ed.), *NA - Advances in Consumer Research*, Association for Consumer Research Provo, UT, pp. 496-499.
- xxii. De Jager & Gbadamosi (2013), "Predicting students' satisfaction through service quality in higher education", *The International Journal of Management Education*, 11(3):107-118
- xxiii. De Oliveira, O. J., & Ferreira, E. C. (2009, May). "Adaptation and application of the ERVQUAL scale in higher education". *Proceedings of POMS 20th annual conference*, Orlando, FL.
- xxiv. Douglas, J., McClelland, R. and Davies, J. (2008), "The development of a conceptual model of student satisfaction with their experience in higher education", *Quality Assurance in Education*, Vol. 16 No. 1, pp. 19-35.
- xxv. Elliot, K.M. & Healy, M.A. (2001). "Key factors influencing student satisfaction related to recruitment and retention". *Journal of Marketing for Higher Education*, 10 (4), 1-11.
- xxvi. Elliott, K.M. and Shin, D. (2002), "Student satisfaction; an alternative approach to assessing this important concept", *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, Vol. 24, pp. 197-209.